

response ranged from 0.4 to 37.0%. Zhing hua #5 and Habiganj Boro VIII had the best response (see table).

Two wk after induction, the anther calli were transferred to MS regeneration

medium supplemented with 0.5 mg IAA/litre and 1.0 mg kinetin/litre. The percentage of root development was 30.8 to 100%. Albinism was higher than green plant regeneration (see table).

High callusing ability of varieties indicates their potential to be cultured in a nutrient medium, which indicates the need for screening rice germplasm for callusing ability. □

Culture conditions and callus-forming ability of rice anthers

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More efficient anther culture techniques, especially for indica rices, are needed to speed varietal development through anther culture.

The callusing ability (CA) of anthers of 3 indica and indica/japonica varieties, and 4 F₂ lines in 5 different media ranged from 0 to 25.0% (Table 1). IR19660-311 and Pajam responded to five media and an F₂ line of BR7/Basmati 370 responded to two. The CA of the anthers of these varieties or lines was different in different media, but N6, a medium developed in China for japonica varieties, did not perform as well as the other media, especially for the pure indicas. The CA of the anthers of these varieties or lines differed significantly when cultured in the five media, indicating the existence of genotypic variability among them (Table 1).

CA of Pajam anthers ranged from 0.0 to 6.9 under light (mean 2.2%) and 4.0 to 9.0% in darkness (mean 7.0%) (Table 2). The difference between these two means was significant, indicating that the CA may be increased by manipulating incubation conditions. Similarly, the differentiation of calli into green plants was comparatively higher with anthers obtained from modified H5 medium and dark incubation. However, regeneration into albino plants was more frequent than into green plants (Table 2). □

Table 1. Response of anthers of indica, indica/japonica varieties, and F₂ lines to callus induction in different media, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Varieties and lines	Callus-forming ability ^a (%) in the media					Mean ^b
	N6	Modified N6	H5	Modified H5	SK-8	
BG96-3/J2	0.0	10.0	7.1	11.1	12.5	8.1 b
IR19660-311	6.9	12.3	22.7	25.0	14.1	16.2 a
Pajam	3.2	2.6	3.8	8.3	5.7	4.7 bcd
IR3249-19-1-3/Hbj. Boro	0.0	5.0	7.0	12.2	5.7	6.1 bc
IV (F ₂)						
IR2003-P3-3-1-2/Amboro	0.0	1.3	1.0	2.4	5.3	3.2 ale
II (F ₂)						
BR7/Baimati 370 (F ₂)	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.1	1.2	0.7 e
Dymisia/IR424-2-1-57414 (F ₂)	0.0	1.3	3.2	3.8	1.8	2.0 de
Mean	0.5	4.4 a	3.7 a	6.8 a	5.4 a	—

^a Callus-forming ability (%) = $\frac{\text{no. of anthers producing callus}}{\text{no. of anthers inoculated}} \times 100$.

^b Means followed by different letters are significantly different at P0.05 level.

Table 2. Effect of media and incubation condition on callus-forming ability and differentiation of Pajam, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Medium	Incubation ^a condition	Anthers inoculated (no.)	Callus produced		Differentiation ^b (%)		
			No.	%	Roots only	Albino plants	Green plants
N6	Light	180	3	1.7	66.7	33.3	—
	Dark	160	8	5.0	60.0	20.0	—
Modified N6	Light	110	0	0.0	—	—	—
	Dark	200	8	4.0	33.3	33.3	—
H5	Light	150	1	0.7	100.0	—	—
	Dark	115	9	7.8	66.7	22.2	11.1
Modified H5	Light	145	10	6.9	66.7	16.7	16.7
	Dark	290	26	9.0	56.7	13.3	20.2
SK-8	Light	175	3	1.7	33.3	33.3	—
	Dark	300	24	8.0	50.0	21.4	7.1
Total	Light	760	17	2.2 b	61.5	23.1	7.7
	Dark	1065	75	7.0 a ^c	51.0	20.4	10.2

^a Light = inoculated anthers were incubated under light for 13 h/d (about 2500 lux) at 26±1 °C. Dark = inoculated anthers were initially incubated in darkness for 15 d and then under light for 13 h/d at 26±1°C for the rest of the period. ^b Calculated on the basis of number of calli transferred for differentiation in M.S. medium supplemented with 0.5 mg IAA and 1.0 mg kinetin/litre. ^c Significantly different at P0.05 level.

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